

Developing a Testing Environment for Parameter Optimization of Dynamic Movement Primitives

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Abstract. Dynamic Movement Primitives (DMPs) provide a flexible approach for generating goal-directed trajectories. The quality of the trajectories depends on a set of various internal parameters of the DMP. Despite their widespread application, quantitative guidelines for their parametrization are largely absent in literature. Therefore, the present work introduces the methodological foundation for a structured exploration of DMP parameter effects. Building upon the Python codebase `dmpbb0` for DMPs, which provides the core DMP implementation, an environment consisting of three highly reusable frameworks is developed. It enables systematic parameter exploration: one for small-scale manual trajectory generation, one for large-scale automated trajectory generation, and one for trajectory evaluation based on numerous criteria. Thus, future analyses for determining use case-specific optimal parameters can be carried out with the frameworks. As an application example, a Universal Robots UR5 is considered; in general, the environment can be utilized for trajectory generation in any robotic system. This extended abstract focuses on the design of the software environment, which will enable future systematic parameter studies.

Keywords: Dynamic Movement Primitives, Parameter Optimization, Trajectory Generation, Automated Testing.

1 Introduction

Dynamic movement primitives (DMPs) constitute a mathematical framework based on nonlinear differential equations, designed to generalize goal-directed motion in robotic systems. By encoding demonstration trajectories, DMPs enable the generation of motion that replicates the original trajectory while adapting to new goals or conditions. This allows their application in a multitude of scenarios demanding flexible, natural, and real-time trajectory generation. Since their initial introduction by Ijspeert et al. [1] in 2002, DMPs have remained a subject of ongoing research aimed at improving their performance and applicability in robotics.

A key contributor in this field in recent years is Stulp, who together with Raiola published the codebase `dmpbb0` for *dynamic movement primitives and black box optimization* [2]. Based on its Python implementation, the goal of the present research is twofold: First, a comprehensive testing environment is developed around `dmpbb0`'s core functionality to enable manual as well as automated DMP-based trajectory generation with systematic parameter variation. Second, in a future step, systematic test runs will be conducted on this enhanced environment to determine concrete recommendations for DMP parametrization. The created tool allows for obtaining use case-specific optimal parameters for DMP training, thereby supporting human planners in their decision-making process when planning trajectories based on DMPs. A Universal Robots UR5, an industrial six-degree-of-freedom collaborative robotic arm, serves as the platform for the present research. In general, however, the developed framework can be used on any robotic system requiring trajectory planning. Such versatility aligns with the established view that DMPs are applicable across a wide range of robotic contexts [3].

This extended abstract presents the design of the study and the enhanced software environment. Future work will employ this tool to conduct comprehensive parameter studies for specific robotic applications.

2 Methodology

Building upon the modular components of the `dmpbb0` library, three frameworks are developed. The *User Interaction Framework* allows a human planner to first create a minimal jerk [4] demonstration trajectory, then train a DMP file based on the trajectory and a DMP parameter set, and finally execute the DMP based on an execution context. The execution context defines, for instance, a new goal state, new time scaling, or obstacles to be avoided. Thereby, a new trajectory is obtained. One important design choice is the file naming convention employed, allowing to backtrack parameter choices. To reduce errors and improve the user experience, a graphical user interface is developed for all scripts.

Moreover, this system is enhanced with additional functionality to allow for automated testing, called the *Automated Testing Framework*. Its addition supports the systematic execution of parameterized trials, aligning with principles from Design of Experiments [5] to ensure structured and reproducible testing. This framework establishes a three-dimensional testing structure: Multiple demonstration trajectories are utilized in conjunction with multiple DMP parameter sets to create DMPs, which are then executed on multiple execution contexts. To obtain such large numbers of DMP parameter sets, an additional script utilizes Latin Hypercube Sampling [6]. Latin Hypercube Sampling is a stratified sampling technique that efficiently explores high-dimensional parameter spaces by ensuring representative coverage across all parameter dimensions.

Lastly, an *Analysis and Interpretation Framework* is developed from the ground up. It offers various tools that are applied on the resulting trajectory files. A visualization script creates Cartesian plots and joint-wise motion profiles for a first qualitative assessment. Quantitative data is obtained by an analysis script that creates a tabular test report; each row corresponds to an analyzed trajectory, whereas the columns include numerous criteria to assess trajectory performance. These criteria include, for instance: script runtime; maximum and root mean square values of velocity, acceleration, and jerk; goal deviation; or offsets in velocity and acceleration at the initial and goal states. Extensive test reports resulting from a substantial number of trajectories can be interpreted automatically. Based on a data frame that includes the test report’s information, another script outputs various statistical measures for the aforementioned criteria, such as minimum, mean, or feature importance. They allow an assessment of which tested trajectories – and thus which parameter values – achieve optimal performance with respect to the specified criteria.

The structure of the Automated Testing Framework and the Analysis and Interpretation Framework as well as their associated workflow is visualized in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Structural overview of the developed testing environment, presenting the Automated Testing Framework and the Analysis and Interpretation Framework. Within the frameworks, dark-shaded elements denote Python scripts, whereas light-shaded elements denote data files of various file types. Arrows indicate the direction of the workflow.

3 Conclusion

Based on `dmpbbo`, an environment for DMP-based trajectory planning and large-scale trajectory testing is developed. It is made up of three frameworks that allow manual and automated trajectory generation as well as their qualitative and quantitative evaluation. The aim is to offer a tool for finding use case-specific optimums for the internal DMP parameters. In future work, this tool will be employed to perform systematic parameter studies for specific robotic applications.

Acknowledgement. This research has been partially funded by the MASTERLY project, which received funding from the European Union’s research and innovation program Horizon Europe under the grant agreement 101091800.

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